

Magnetic, Spectral and Thermal Properties of Cu(II) Complexes of 5-Phenyl azo-Salicylaldehydes.

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Cu(II) complexes of 5-phenyl azo-salicylaldehyde(PAS), o-chloro-PAS, m-chloro-PAS, o-toluene azo-salicylaldehyde (o-TAS), m-TAS and p-TAS have been synthesised and their spectral and magnetic properties reported. TGA and non-isothermal decomposition of Cu(II) complex of p-TAS are incidentally carried out. It is found that decomposition of the complex took place in a single step with an order of reaction nearly zero and the activation energy 16.20 kcal/mole.

THOUGH some work on azo-dye metal complexes was carried out in the past¹⁻³ and studies on similar complexes are being carried out at present, as seen from the reviews recently published⁴⁻⁶, a careful search of literature revealed that azo-dye, 5-phenyl azo-salicylaldehyde, did not receive an attention it deserved in the field of structural chemistry. A stray paper by Ohta *et al.*⁷ mentioned the preparation of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of 5-aryl-azo-salicylaldehyde. Mohan Das and Trivedi⁸ described the spectral studies of some U(VI) and Pd(II) complexes of 5-phenyl-azo-salicylaldehyde. It was, therefore, thought by the present workers, that 5-phenyl azo-salicylaldehyde, with substituents in various positions will be ideal ligands for preparation of complexes especially of transition metal ions and characterising their structural properties.

Experimental

Preparation of azo-dyes and their metal complexes :

The method used for the preparation of the ligands was similar to that of Trivedi and Mohan Das⁸.

Copper complexes with phenyl azo-salicylaldehyde, o-toluene azo-salicylaldehyde, p-toluene azo-salicylaldehyde were obtained by the addition of copper acetate (AnalaR) in ethanol (0.01M) to the ligand solution in ethanol (0.02M). The coloured precipitates thus formed were filtered, washed, and then dried in vacuum desiccator. In the preparation of copper complex with o-chloro-PAS, copper acetate in ethanol-benzene mixture (1 : 1, 0.01M) was added to the ligand solution in ethanol-benzene mixture (1 : 1, 0.02M). The yellow coloured precipitate, thus obtained, was filtered, washed and dried in vacuum desiccator. For the preparation of copper complex with p-chloro phenyl azo-salicylaldehyde, the ligand in benzene-ethanol (1 : 1, 0.02M) was taken and 20 ml of alcoholic ammonia (20%, v/v) were added to it. The ligand dissolves in the mixture completely. Cupric nitrate, in ethanol (0.01M), was then added to above solution when a yellowish green, precipitate separated out, which was filtered, washed, and dried in vacuum desiccator. The results of elemental analyses of these complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Cu(II) complex of	Copper %		Nitrogen %		M.P./decomp. °C	Colour of the complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Diffuse reflectance spectra (nm)
	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found				
PAS	12.37	12.44	10.90	10.24	265	Yellowish green	1.94	620sh, 680, 940.
o-chloro-PAS	10.90	10.84	9.61	10.20	290	Yellow	1.68	520 sh, 680.
m-chloro-PAS	10.90	10.00	9.61	9.68	300	Yellow	1.69	520sh, 680, 980
p-chloro-PAS	10.90	10.79	9.61	10.00	250	Yellowish green	2.09	540, 680, 980.
o-TAS	11.73	11.55	10.34	10.61	282	Yellowish brown	1.93	580, 660.
m-TAS	11.73	10.79	10.34	10.42	300	Yellowish green	1.65	620sh, 820.
p-TAS	11.73	11.42	10.34	10.82	300	Yellow	1.86	570, 720, 950.

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Physical measurements

The solid diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer with reflectance attachment SP-540. The disc method was employed, using magnesium oxide as a reference. The magnetic moments at room temperature were measured on Gouy balance. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (model 337). DTA was carried out in Regional Research Laboratory, Hyderabad, with DTA apparatus supplied by Leeds and Northrup, Philadelphia (USA). TGA was carried out using a Stanton balance in Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. Non-isothermal decomposition of Cu(II) complex of *p*-TAS and the treatment of data was carried out according to the method prescribed by Freeman and Carroll⁹.

Results and Discussion

The diffuse reflectance spectra (Table 1) of copper(II) complexes of PAS, *m*-chloro-PAS, *p*-chloro-PAS and *m*-TAS show an absorption around 940–980 nm which is a sure indication of a planar configuration for these complexes¹⁰. Again a band around 680 nm located in all these complexes, under study, point out to a square planar or distorted octahedral configuration for these complexes on the basis of an extensive literature survey^{11–14}.

Though the room temperature magnetic moments of the Cu(II) complex of PAS, *p*-chloro-PAS and *o*-TAS (Table 1) are but slightly higher than those expected for square planar symmetry¹⁵, they are undoubtedly lower than those reported for tetrahedral geometry

for such complexes. The tetrahedral geometry for the present complexes is clearly ruled out since the spectral data for them draw a clear blank in the region 25000–14200 cm^{-1} .¹⁶ The slightly low magnetic moments observed for Cu(II) complexes of *o*-chloro-PAS, *m*-chloro-PAS and *m*-TAS suggest a polymeric nature of the complexes.

Coordination, during complexation, is through -OH and CHO as is evident from disappearance of -OH stretch frequency (3200 cm^{-1}) bending frequency (1280 cm^{-1}) and in-plane deformation frequency (1200 cm^{-1}) and considerable shift in C=O frequency (from 1640–1600 cm^{-1} in ligands to 1600 cm^{-1}) (Table 2). The splitting of the C=O frequency in the copper(II) complexes of *m*-chloro-PAS, *o*-TAS, *m*-TAS and *p*-TAS suggests a lowering of symmetry. There is a significant change in N=N stretching frequency (1500 and 1375 cm^{-1} as compared to 1550–1575 cm^{-1} and 1460–1490 cm^{-1} in the ligands) and a new band seems to have appeared at 1425 cm^{-1} after complexation. This suggests long-bond type of interaction of N=N bond with neighbouring metal atoms.

In the case of present complexes of copper(II), it is evident that predominant factor in the structure is square planar, but due to this very fact the molecules are stacked above each other and there is a weak interaction between the copper atoms and the juxtaposed -N=N- of the ligands. This longer Cu-N bond gives the complex slightly distorted octahedral structure and the low magnetic moments.

TGA of Cu(II) complex of *p*-TAS showed three distinct steps at 210°–310°, 310°–340° and 340°–620°

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRA (ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES IN CM^{-1})

Name of the azosilylaldehyde	Free ligand			Cu(II) complex of			
	-OH	C=O	N=N	-OH	C=O	N=N	Additional
PAS	3200b 1280s 1200s	1650s	1550s 1450s	—	1605s	1500s 1375s	1425s 1450s
<i>o</i> -chloro-PAS	3200b 1272s 1200s	1650s	1555s 1460s	—	1605s	1500s 1375s	—
<i>m</i> -chloro-PAS	3200b 1280s 1200s	1660s	1575s 1490s	—	1600s 1605s	1520s 1400s	1455s
<i>p</i> -chloro-PAS	3200b 1280s 1190s	1660s	1550s 1460s	3300m	1565s	1530s 1375s	1460s
<i>o</i> -TAS	1275s 1200s	1640s	1560s 1370s	—	1600s 1580s	1500s 1375s	1425s
<i>m</i> -TAS	3200b 1280s 1200s	1650s	1575s 1475s	3060–2850w,b	1600s 1595s	1510s 1450s	1440s 1460s
<i>p</i> -TAS	3160b 1200s	1640s	1555s 1460s	—	1605s 1595sh	1500s 1360s	1450s

b = broad; s = sharp; m = medium; w = weak.

showing weight loss of 2.0, 31.5 and 52.0% respectively. DTA of Cu(II) complex of *o*-TAS showed no endothermic peaks but the decomposition starts with exothermic peak at 300°. The results show absence of water molecule in the Cu(II) complexes.

The treatment of data of the non-isothermal decomposition, according to Freeman and Carroll⁹ is given in Table 3 for the decomposition of Cu(II) complex of *p*-TAS. The first and second steps are

TABLE 3—NON-ISOTHERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF CU(II) COMPLEX OF *p*-TOLUENE-AZO-SALICYLALDEHYDE

$[\Delta \log(dw/dt)/\Delta \log w_r]$ (Y-values)	$[\Delta(1/T)/\Delta \log w_r] \times 10^3, ^\circ\text{K}^{-1}$ (X-values)
5.382	1.520
5.122	1.447
4.560	1.315
4.477	1.282
4.356	1.215

Order of reaction = 0.137

Energy of activation = 16.20 kcal/mole, obtained from the plot of X vs Y values and by Freeman-Carroll method.

too fast to be studied and hence the data recorded above are only for the third step. It is seen that the reaction takes place in a single step non-isothermally and is of nearly zero order, the order of reaction and the activation energy being 0.137 and 16.20 kcal/mole respectively by the least square method.

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